

Best-selling small-molecule drug: Discovery of Eliquis®/Apixaban, a Novel Factor Xa Anticoagulant.

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Abstract:

Thrombosis is the leading cause of death in developed countries. There is a significant need for novel antithrombotics with an improved safety profile to replace Warfarin which has been in use for ~60 years and has significant bleeding issues. Factor Xa is at the junction of the intrinsic and extrinsic pathways of the coagulation cascade. Preclinical data has demonstrated that blocking FXa is an effective approach for anticoagulation with improved safety profile. Utilizing structure based drug design tools, focused screening, and ADMET innovations, we at Bristol-Myers Squibb/DuPont had discovered a novel class of potent, selective and orally bioavailable Factor Xa inhibitors culminating in Eliquis®/Apixaban. Eliquis® is currently the top selling small molecule drug with annual sales of ~\$10B. In 2015, the Eliquis discovery team received the American Chemical Society Heroes of Chemistry Award for a successful commercial product that improves human well-being.

During the optimization process, we have also discovered the powerful Chan Lam Coupling reaction of copper promoted C-X bond cross-coupling via boronic acids, a complementary reaction to the Nobel prize Suzuki Miyaura C-C bond Coupling reaction. In addition, at the molecular recognition frontier, we have pioneered the first rational use of halogen bonding in structure-based drug design.

Eliquis®/Apixaban

Keywords:

Factor Xa inhibitors, Eliquis®, apixaban, structure-based drug design, Chan-Lam reaction, halogen bonding.

References:

- Discovery of 1-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-7-oxo-6-(4-(2-oxopiperidin-1-yl)phenyl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro 1H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-3-carboxamide (Apixaban, BMS-562247), a Highly Potent, Selective, Efficacious, and Orally Bioavailable Inhibitor of Blood Coagulation Factor Xa." Pinto, D. J. P.; Orwat, M. J.; Koch, S.; Rossi, K. A.; Alexander, R. S.; Smallwood, A.; Wong, P. C.; Rendina, A. R.; Luetzgen, J. M.; Knabb, R. M.; He, K.; Xin, B.; Wexler, R. R.; Lam, P. Y. S. J. Med. Chem. 2007, 50, 5339-5356.
- Copper-promoted Carbon-Heteroatom bond cross-coupling with boronic acids and derivatives". Qiao, J. X.; Lam, P. Y. S. Syn. 2011, 829-856.
- Halogen bonding- a world parallel to hydrogen-bonding" Symposium in Organic Division, #58, ACS, August 16-20, 2009. Washington DC. Highlighted in C&E News, Sep 21, 2009, p39-42, "...to the best of our knowledge, this is the first successful use of halogen bonding in rational drug design..."

Quinazoline-3(4H)-One Analogs As An Important Class Of Analgesic Drug Discovery

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Abstract:

The development of new drugs has been responsible for decreasing human morbidity and mortality more than any other scientific endeavor during our lifetime. In recent years, a large number of pharmacologically important heterocyclic compound have been synthesized and are being widely used as drugs. The heterocyclic containing nitrogen, quinazolinone nucleus exhibit a wide spectrum of biological activities.

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAID) are important therapeutic drug category for the treatment of inflammation in addition to analgesic and antipyretic activities. NSAID's are used for rheumatoid arthritis and other inflammatory diseases starting from Aspirin to the recent selective COX-2 inhibitors. It has evident from the literature that, the anti-inflammatory response of the NSAID is either inhibiting the prostaglandin H synthase or cyclooxygenase (COX) enzyme. However, the chronic use of NSAID's leads to potential for gastrointestinal bleeding, heart attack or stroke. Due to their suboptimal therapeutic profile, the search for non-opioid analgesics to replace this well-established therapeutics remains a critical pursuit and NSAID's is also has limitations due to the poor GI tolerance even though it have been widely used clinically. Therefore, investigation of new NSAIDs is still a major challenge and production of safer and more active NSAIDs and analgesic drugs are need.

Quinazolin-4(3H)-ones are potential bioactive agents which are having significant therapeutic effect with substitution at 1st / 2nd / 3rd position of quinazolin-4(3H)-ones. A series of 2,3-disubstituted-4(3H)-quinazolin-4-one derivatives were synthesized by reacting anthranilic acid with substituted benzoyl chloride followed by condensing with hydrazine hydrate. The 3-amino -2-substituted quinazolinone has further subjected to Schiff base with isatin /aliphatic or aromatic aldehyde and mannich products were obtained from the reaction of amines with isatin based Schiff bases. The results of the various study conducted indicates that quinazoline pharmacophore is having vast therapeutic potential, which attracts strong interest to explore in medicinal chemistry for the drug discovery and development.

Keywords:

Quinazolin-4(3H)-one, Schiff bases, Analgesic, Isatin, Mannich base.

L-Arginine, Nitric Oxid (NO) and Triple Omega (3, 6, 9) on a green seaweed (Ceulepra SP) for preventive and prolong life.

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NanoMedicine, and Pharmacy STIKES Halmahera.'

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Abstract:

Green algae seaweed Ceulepra SP group is a group of Thallus, sphere-shaped, sheet, there are many in the sea, Maluku.

Do some research to see the content of amino acids and other compounds contained such, L-Arginine, Glutamic Acid, Oleic Acid, Linolol Acid, and Linolenic Acid. In the first ingredient of green seaweed, algae grem Wine.

L-Arginineas a compound formed Nitric Oxid (NO) plays an active role for the endothelium of blood vessels, flexibility, as well as making up arteriol vasodilation in the brain, the cardiovascular Vasculasasi to prevent atherosclerotic, as well as provide Vasculasasi the prostate, thus improving the improved functioning of Sexual Vitality.

Arginine segor 165 + 72.83 mg (100 g), Rebus 177.5 + 36.06 mg / 100 g. Oleic acid (13.78%), linolol acid (33.58%), linolenic acid (5.94%).

The role of omega crucial triple to extend life by improving the quality of the blood vessels in the brain, heart, prostate and other organs. Green sea grass Ceulepra SP also contains Phytol (Chlorophyll) is high (16.63%) and has a high flavonoids as antioxidants (AO) with the complete antioxidant + nitric oxid + Triple Omega then very strong and healthy body as the body is fulfilled by the well stocked compounds acids, amino, antioxidants and nutrients the brain. The combination of AO + NO + Nuto + Triple Omega determines the quality of life, preventing atherosclerotic and prolong life expectancy.

The full sources of the compounds contained in seaweed green Ceulepra SP, then a good impact to prevent atherosclerotic, stroke, heart attack, and impotence. By eating regularly, the size of the dose will impact a person's health to the body.

Keywords:

Arginine, Nitric Oxid, Triple Omega, Phytol, Atherosclerotic, longevity.

Green Bio-Based Polymeric Materials: Dreams And Sustainable Development

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Abstract:

Bio-based (green) materials from biomass / biowaste / renewable resources have attracted increased attention due to the public concerns about the depletion of fossil fuels and climate change, and feasible alternatives to traditional petroleum-based polymers. Biomass has been considered to be the only sustainable source of organic carbon in earth and the perfect equivalent to petroleum for the production of fuels and fine chemicals with net zero carbon emission. Biomass resources can provide an interesting sustainable platform to substitute partially, and to some extent totally, petroleum-based polymers through the design of bio-based polymers that can compete or even surpass the existing petroleum-based materials on a cost-performance basis with a positive environmental impact. The development of biopolymers based materials made from renewable resources is an active research area that is attracting increasing scientific and industrial attention due to many applications in packing, textiles, electronics, sensors, energy storage, pharmaceutical, cosmetics, agriculture, and biomedical. Impressive advances in bio-based biodegradable polymeric materials based on bio(nano)polymer composites, composites films, and multifunctional composites, have been made in recent decades. Attempts to transfer biomass to produce industrially useful biopolymers and fine chemicals by traditional biotechnological approaches have obtained only very limited success. An effective biomass conversion requires the interdisciplinary research field which is a unique combination of biotechnology, chemistry, materials science and engineering. The lecture will explore the state and art of green bio-based polymeric materials and their applications with the impact of green chemistry and engineering.

Biography:

Dr. Chinnappan Baskar is Professor and Director, Research and Development Center, Teerthanker Mahaveer University, Moradabad – 24001, Uttar Pradesh, India. He was a Former Director (Officiating) of THDC Institute of Hydropower Engineering and Technology Tehri, Constituent Institute of Uttarakhand Technical University, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India; BK21 Research Professor, Department of Environmental Engineering and Biotechnology, Myongji University, South Korea, and Chairperson of YSB Foundation, Dehradun. He has received his M. Sc. Chemistry from the Indian Institute of Technology Madras and PhD in Organic and Materials Chemistry from the Department of Chemistry, National University of Singapore (NUS), Singapore. His research interests include synthetic organic chemistry, conducting polymers, green chemistry and engineering, ionic liquids, biomass conversion, green materials, biodegradable polymers, bio-based plastics, renewable energy, smart textiles, wearable/flexible electronics, sensors, and radiation resistant polymers. He has published several research papers in reputed international journals with high impact factor, and conference proceedings. He was invited to attend and deliver lectures/seminars in international and national conferences & workshops, and faculty development programs. He has received the Distinguished Academician Award from Pentagram Research Center (P) Ltd. He is the Editor of Biomass Conversion: The Interface of Biotechnology, Chemistry and Materials Science (Springer-Verlag New York); author of Engineering Chemistry book (Wiley India); co-author of text book Stereochemistry (Narosa Publishing House and Alpha Science International Ltd); and the co-author of text book Systematic Nomenclature of Organic Compounds (IK International Publishers, Delhi).

Best-selling small-molecule drug: Discovery of Eliquis®/ Apixaban leading to Chan-Lam Coupling Reaction and First Rational Use of Halogen Bonding in Drug Design

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Abstract:

Thrombosis is the leading cause of death in developed countries. There is a significant need for novel antithrombotics with an improved safety profile to replace Warfarin which has been in use for ~60 years and has significant bleeding issues. We at Bristol-Myers Squibb/DuPont had discovered a novel class of potent, selective and orally bio-available Factor Xa inhibitors culminating in Eliquis®/Apixaban. Eliquis® is currently the best-selling small-molecule drug with annual sales of ~\$10B.

During the optimization process, we have also discovered the powerful Chan-Lam Coupling reaction of copper promoted C-X bond cross-coupling via boronic acids, a complementary reaction to the Nobel prize Suzuki-Miyaura C-C bond Coupling reaction. C-L reaction is currently used in manufacturing of an antipsychotic drug.

In addition, at the molecular recognition front-tier, we have pioneered the first rational use of halogen bonding in structure-based drug design.

A. Eliquis®/Apixaban

B. Chan-Lam Coupling Reaction

C. First rational use of halogen bonding in drug design

Keywords:

Factor Xa inhibitors, Eliquis®, apixaban, structure-based drug design, Chan-Lam reaction, halogen bonding.

References:

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